

Formative Assessment in Engineering Courses at PUJ: Faculty Perspectives on Assessment.

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Abstract

The role of assessment is pivotal in the teaching-learning process, serving as a guiding tool for students to understand the necessary improvements to achieve competency. While summative assessment remains prevalent in teacher-centered learning approaches, a shift towards curriculum reform, such as the CDIO initiative at the School of Engineering, Pontificia Universidad Javeriana, is fostering a transition towards more active, student-centered pedagogical practices. Given the fundamental nature of evaluation in teaching, this study integrates data from surveys and interviews to explore faculty evaluative practices and their conceptualizations of assessment. Key factors essential for effective feedback and transparency within the assessment framework, including the communication of learning outcomes and assessment criteria, undergo thorough examination. Findings reveal that approximately half of the faculty members prioritize encouraging students' critical reflection on their learning processes, aligning with their feedback strategies. However, some faculty still lean towards grading of student knowledge. This study lays the groundwork for continued discussion on assessment processes within the School of Engineering

Keywords: Active Learning; Engineering Education; Assessment; Feedback, Faculty.

1 Introduction

The need to train professionals with the skills for the 21st century has driven the transformation of teaching practices in engineering education. Gradually, changes have been made from teacher-centered teaching to student-centered teaching. In this kind of teaching, meaning is achieved by students when they actively select and cumulatively construct their knowledge through individual and social activities (Biggs, 2001). The changes in the focus of student-centered teaching lead to the alignment of the elements that are part of teaching and that not only concern the teacher-student relationship but also the types of tasks, infrastructure, pedagogical practices, and evaluation systems Kolmos (2004). According to Biggs (2001), the optimization of the educational process is achieved when learning objectives, pedagogical strategies, and evaluations are coherently integrated. Formative assessment particularly proposes a tool as that allows continuous and meaningful feedback on learning progress. Assessment allows both teachers and students to obtain information from the evaluation process and act either to improve the learning process or so that the student can demonstrate their progress in achieving the result (Black and Wiliam, 2018). Formative assessment facilitates the development of metacognitive and self-regulatory skills, allowing students to identify their strengths and areas for improvement (Black and Wiliam, 1998). The transition of teachers from a culture of summative assessment to formative assessment remains challenging, despite the development of skills that allow the student to learn to learn (Lopez-Caudana et al., 2020), necessary for the development of 21st-century skills.

Effective feedback practice includes clarity of assessment criteria, timeliness of feedback, and encouraging student reflection on their own learning. Nicol, D. J., and Macfarlane-Dick, D., (2006) propose a model of effective feedback practice that indicates the seven principles that should be included: helps clarify what good

performance is, facilitates the development of self-assessment (reflection) in learning; delivers high-quality information to students about their learning; encourages teacher and peer dialogue around learning; encourages positive motivational beliefs and self-esteem; provides opportunities to close the gap between current and desired performance; finally, Provides information to teachers that can be used to help shape teaching.

The above described has important implications for teaching practice and assessment design. Sambell et al. (2013) highlight the relevance of the design of evaluation tasks as a fundamental element to be able to provide effective feedback. The evaluation tasks provide important information regarding the educational approach based on the answers that come from two questions: why evaluate? and what to evaluate. (Ibarra-Sáiz, M.S., 2023). The responses may demonstrate three evaluative approaches: learning evaluation, which seeks to report on the student's competence about learning outcomes; assessment as learning, which allows teachers to determine the next steps to advance student learning; and evaluation as learning that guides and provides opportunities for each student to monitor and critically reflect on their learning and identify the next steps to follow.

Guaranteeing the quality of teaching is based on the orientation proposed by Biggs, which in practice has led universities to adopt educational models with constructivist frameworks of reference. Particularly at the Pontificia Universidad Javeriana, the CDIO (Conceive-Design-Implement-Operate) model was adopted for the reform of engineering programs. Implementing this model requires that faculty be equipped with the understanding of how to implement changes and be provided with relevant guidance and resources (Crawley, et al., 2014). After three years of implementation of the CDIO model in the Faculty of Engineering of the Pontificia Universidad Javeriana (PUJ), it is relevant to understand how the proposed educational models affect the practices of teachers, and particularly evaluation processes.

2 Methodology

The research question was answered through a qualitative exploratory methodology. The research aimed to understand the nature of evaluations conducted by the faculty of the Faculty of Engineering of the PUJ. The data was collected through a survey, and responses were analyzed through categorization to identify emerging patterns. The questionnaire was based on Ibarra-Sáiz's research and included open-ended questions to triangulate the information and draw conclusive insights about evaluative practices of the professors. Three types of questions were asked: The first group of questions sought to understand the evaluative intention, such as what is being evaluated and what it's being evaluated for. The answers were presented in a predefined manner according to the conceptualization given by Ibarra-Sáinz. Respondents were asked to organize the relevance of these questions according to their conceptions of evaluation. The second group of questions was extracted from the scale presented by Ibarra-Sáinz to measure the perceptions of university professors regarding evaluative procedures. Table 1 presents the questions asked, and respondents were asked to answer with a frequency scale ranging from always to never.

A final group of questions corresponded to those that provided detailed information about the teacher's practice. The following open-ended questions were asked: What is feedback for you? How do you give feedback? What do you consider to be the essential factors for good feedback?

Table 1. Questions for understanding evaluative practice.

Questions

Do you give feedback?
Do you give feedback on non-evaluative work?
Do you give feedback on an evaluative work?
Learning outcomes, criteria, assessment procedures and grading system of the course are public
The evaluation system informs about what students must deliver or execute
The evaluation system informed about the evaluation criteria and instruments
The evaluation system informs of the four modalities (self-evaluation, peer evaluation, shared evaluation, evaluation by the teacher).
Assessment tasks, students must perform, are informed and described
Assessment tasks involve the student's use of relevant knowledge and content of the course
Assessment tasks are presented as a challenge for the student
Assessment tasks facilitate the application of knowledge and skills to real-life situations or cases
Feedback is provided to students on their progress during the teaching-learning process
It makes it easier for students to participate and provide self-feedback by contrasting their progress with the assessment instruments provided to them previously
Students receive feedback on their progress from their peers through peer review
It makes it easier for students to collaborate in defining some elements of the assessment system
Students self-evaluate their products or performances, either individually or in groups
Evaluation and graded is taken place in a dialogic way (between teachers and students) and by consensus

Regarding the data analysis tools used in the survey, a simple trend analysis was conducted on each question to identify general patterns. Subsequently, mosaic plots were employed, which are graphical representations of two-way contingency tables, to visualize the relationship between two or more qualitative variables. Additionally, a Sieve Diagram, a graphical method for visualizing frequencies in a two-way contingency table and comparing them to expected frequencies under the assumption of independence, was utilized. This technique allowed for a deeper evaluation of the associations between the variables under study. Following this, an analysis of open-ended questions was performed, where the most recurrent themes for each question were identified, the most representative words from the responses were extracted, and their relationship with the themes was explored using the Dirichlet algorithm. Finally, a sentiment analysis was conducted to detect polarities in the responses and possible correlations among them. This approach provided a more comprehensive understanding of the attitudes and emotions expressed by the respondents, aiding in identifying underlying patterns and significant trends in the collected data. The combination of these techniques allowed us to identify correlations, coherence, and inconsistencies in the responses, as well as to determine with the responses to other survey questions what could be the origin of such inconsistencies.

3 Results and Analysis

The survey revealed a diverse distribution among the surveyed professors. Of the total respondents, 14 professors belong to or teach in the field of electronic engineering, 12 in civil engineering, and 2 in industrial engineering. Among these, 16 are full time professors and 12 are partial time professors. Regarding the distribution by semester, it is observed that most professors teach in the seventh or eighth semester, with a significant number also in the first and second semesters. A trend analysis regarding the question about evaluation criteria identified five main categories: progress, measurement, thinking, and combinations of these priorities. Most professors prioritize measurement and progress, followed by thinking. In terms of evaluation objectives, three main aspects were identified: certifying student competence, guiding their learning, and providing information to faculty. Most professors consider evaluation primarily serves to guide student learning, followed by certifying their competence and providing information to faculty.

It is relevant to note that most respondents have experience teaching in multiple semesters, suggesting a wide range of pedagogical skills and a deep understanding of the learning process throughout students' academic careers. This variety in teaching experience may influence the perception and application of evaluation criteria, as well as how evaluation results are used to inform and improve teaching. Professors with more experience at different levels of the curriculum may have a more holistic view of student needs and thus adapt their evaluation methods and feedback more effectively. Regarding feedback provided to students, there is a clear preference for providing feedback consistently. Most professors claim to offer feedback always or most of the time, while only a few indicate that they occasionally provide this type of feedback. This trend is more pronounced among full time professors, who tend to offer feedback more consistently compared to partial time professors.

Identifying relationships between questions using mosaics suggests a connection between the perception of the evaluation purpose and how evaluation is conducted. Professors who consider evaluation primarily as a measure of student performance tend to evaluate and grade more dialogically, possibly to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the level of competence achieved. On the other hand, professors who view evaluation as a tool to guide the learning process, although they may also evaluate dialogically, tend to do so occasionally, suggesting a more balanced approach between direct feedback and other evaluation methods. The contrast of responses in the mosaics shows a difference in evaluation practices between full time and partial time professors. Full time professors tend to provide feedback on non-evaluative assignments more consistently, which could be related to their greater dedication time at the university. On the other hand, partial time professors tend to provide this feedback occasionally, which could reflect less availability of time due to other responsibilities off-campus. The mosaics suggest that the perception of the evaluation object influences how evaluation is conducted. Professors who see the evaluation object as student progress tend to evaluate non-dialogically most of the time. This may indicate that these professors prioritize observing student progress over time rather than direct interaction during evaluation.

The analysis shows significant correlations in the relationship between feedback offered by professors and the clarity in evaluation criteria and procedures: There is a strong correlation observed between professors who consistently provide feedback and those who consistently make evaluation criteria public. This indicates a consistent transparency and clarity in the expectations set by these professors. Moreover, professors who offer feedback consistently are also those who articulate and elaborate evaluation tasks with precision and clarity. This underscores their commitment to providing clear guidance to students regarding their evaluation expectations. Furthermore, a correlation emerges between professors who consistently provide feedback and those who assign challenging evaluation tasks to students. This suggests an intentional effort on the part of these professors to foster student growth and development through substantial task challenges. Additionally,

the data reveal that professors who consistently offer feedback are inclined to promote the application of knowledge and skills to real-life scenarios in evaluation tasks. This signifies an integrated approach to evaluation, aimed at equipping students with the ability to apply their learning in practical contexts. In summary, the results of the analysis show a close relationship between teachers' feedback practices and transparency in evaluation criteria and procedures. This underscores the importance of clear and consistent communication in the evaluation process to support effective student learning.

The analysis of responses to open questions about feedback reveals several important topics and consistent patterns. We present these topics and some examples of the original responses from the teachers:

- Interaction between teachers and students: Most teachers perceive feedback as an interaction between them and their students in a specific space, allowing them to address elements of the learning process. "A space for interaction between the teacher and their students, where the teacher addresses the assessments conducted with the students."
- Awareness of errors and critical process: Feedback is perceived as a process that allows students to become aware of their mistakes, resolve them, and improve, which is considered fundamental for academic progress. "Solving an exam or an assignment so that the student becomes aware of their mistakes."
- Identification of skills and performance: The importance of feedback in identifying students' skills and performance is highlighted, as well as in communicating their weaknesses and improvement opportunities. "Establishing a bilateral academic dialogue by critical thinking, and reflection - including self-reflection- on the respective academic activities and learning content. It aims to promote student autonomy in learning, appreciation of achievements, improvement of learning methods and processes, and enhancement of professional competencies."
- Relationship with evaluation: Feedback is closely related to the evaluation process, as it allows for identifying shortcomings, learnings, and outcomes, as well as offering improvement opportunities. "Feedback is taking the result of the evaluation, highlighting positive aspects and areas for improvement so that the student can then complement their learning."
- Reflection and development of strengths: The importance of feedback in fostering reflection and the development of students' strengths is mentioned, as well as in identifying areas for improvement and growth opportunities. "It refers to the process of identifying the strengths and weaknesses of the student to provide feedback or information about their performance, with the purpose of enhancing and adjusting their professional progress. "
- Classroom environment as preferred space: Most teachers consider the classroom environment as the preferred space for providing feedback, although other means such as written evaluations or email are also mentioned. "I provide constructive criticism in class, personally, and in a way that the student feels confident with me."
- Emphasis on the evaluation process: Evaluation is highlighted as a key element in the feedback process, as it provides relevant information to improve learning and student performance. "An integral part of the evaluation process, as it involves not only grading but also improvement."
- Respect and mentoring attitude: The importance of maintaining a respectful environment and a mentoring attitude when providing feedback is emphasized, as well as offering constructive and quality feedback. "Transparency, acceptance, truth, and respect are key factors."

To sum up, teachers view feedback as a fundamental process enabling students to reflect on their learning, identify areas for improvement, and enhance their skills. They emphasize the intimate connection between feedback and the evaluation process, along with the significance of fostering a respectful and collaborative

classroom environment. Thus, to the question, "What is feedback for you?", several categories can be identified: Teacher-Student Interaction, where feedback serves as an interaction to address aspects of the learning process; Awareness of Mistakes, as feedback helps students recognize and rectify errors; Identification of Skills and Performance, with feedback playing a vital role in identifying skills and communicating performance; Relationship with Evaluation, as feedback is closely related to the evaluation process to identify weaknesses and lessons learned; and Reflection and Development of Strengths, where feedback is seen as a process that encourages reflection and the development of strengths.

However, when asked about "How do you provide feedback?", it appears that the process is primarily focused on identifying and collecting evaluation evidence. The identified categories include: In-Class Feedback, where the classroom serves as the primary setting for feedback delivery, encompassing written assignments, exams, and group discussions; Socialization of Results, highlighting the importance of sharing evaluation outcomes to grasp their impact on learning; Identification of Errors and Opportunities, viewing feedback as a means to recognize errors and areas for improvement; and Personalization and Adjustment to Rubrics, emphasizing the personalized delivery of feedback tailored to established rubrics. In response to the question, "What are the essential factors for good feedback?", the following categories were identified, aligning with those from previous open questions: Encouragement of Reflection, emphasizing the importance of fostering reflection as a crucial factor for effective feedback; Identification of Skills and Performance, underscoring the significance of recognizing student skills and performance levels; Relationship with Evaluation, highlighting evaluation as a pivotal aspect of good feedback; and Respect and Mentoring Attitude, stressing the importance of maintaining respect and adopting a mentoring approach when delivering feedback.

The result of the sentiment analysis of the open questions generates two poles of analysis, the first focused on the identification of errors and constructive criticism and the second focused on reflection, learning, and continuous improvement. In summary, teachers value feedback as a process of interaction and reflection primarily carried out in the classroom, and consider the relationship with the evaluation process, the encouragement of reflection, and mutual respect essential for effective feedback.

4 Conclusions

There is a significant coherence between evaluation criteria and evaluation objectives. Most teachers prioritize measuring student progress and use evaluation as a tool to guide and improve the learning process. However, their practice focuses on identifying competence levels, but the process of constructive feedback, which teachers themselves value as an essential activity in the learning process, is not evident. Although teachers recognize the importance of feedback in identifying errors and areas for improvement, some seem to focus more on evaluating performance than on the learning process itself.

This could create a discrepancy between the stated intention of feedback and its practical application. The widespread position of teachers is to emphasize the importance of providing feedback to students, both in evaluative and non-evaluative assignments, reflecting significant commitment from teachers to support student learning. However, it is important to consider the diversity of experiences and pedagogical approaches within the faculty when designing evaluation policies and practices, with the aim of ensuring that the individual needs of students are addressed and promoting an inclusive and effective learning environment. Teachers recognize feedback as a fundamental component of the teaching-learning process, allowing students to become aware of their mistakes, identify skills, and improve their performance.

Most teachers consider feedback to be intrinsically linked to performance evaluation and the identification of shortcomings and learnings. At this point, the role of feedback in fostering reflection and the development of

strengths is highlighted, beyond simply identifying errors. Teachers emphasize the importance of creating a learning environment that promotes self-reflection and personal growth of students. Although most teachers mention the importance of written feedback and in-class discussion, some topics suggest that the practical application of feedback may be inconsistent. For example, mentioning written feedback but then focusing on socialization in class could create confusion about the optimal way to provide feedback. The above findings highlight the importance of continuous reflection on teaching practices and assessment of learning, as well as the need for greater clarity and coherence in the implementation of feedback strategies in the classroom. These findings can be attributed to several factors:

- Individual Perception: Each teacher may have a different understanding of what constitutes effective feedback and how it should be applied. This perception may be influenced by their training, previous experience, and teaching style.
- Institutional Focus: Institutional policies and practices can influence how teachers understand and apply feedback. If the institution emphasizes evaluation more than the learning process, teachers are likely to reflect this approach in their responses.
- Lack of Conceptual Clarity: Feedback is a broad concept that can encompass different approaches and practices. The lack of a clear and agreed understanding of what constitutes effective feedback can lead to divergent interpretations and, therefore, inconsistency in its application.
- Time and Resource Constraints: Teachers may face time and resource constraints that affect their ability to provide feedback consistently and comprehensively. This may result in prioritizing certain aspects of feedback over others, contributing to discrepancies in responses.
- Training and Professional Development: Initial and ongoing training of teachers around feedback may vary, affecting their understanding and application of best practices in this area. The lack of professional development opportunities focused on feedback may also contribute to these inconsistencies.

In a second stage of the study with teachers, key aspects related to the feedback process in the educational field will be further explored. Fundamental questions will be raised, such as: How could the feedback process be improved to ensure greater student participation and engagement? and What strategies could be implemented for students to more effectively utilize the feedback received to enhance their learning? Additionally, the barriers and challenges faced by teachers in consistently providing quality feedback will be explored, as well as the impact of students' perceptions and expectations on the effectiveness of this process. Furthermore, the impact of formative feedback on academic performance and student motivation will be investigated.

Concurrently, several future works are projected to expand knowledge in this field. It is proposed to investigate the impact of different approaches and techniques of feedback on academic performance and student self-efficacy. Additionally, the implementation of educational technologies to improve feedback and progress monitoring of students will be explored. Finally, longitudinal studies will be conducted to assess how feedback received during the formative process affects professional development and employability of graduates. These investigations aim to significantly contribute to the continuous improvement of the feedback process in the educational environment.

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